

INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE

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Abstract: The article discusses the measures aimed at the development of science and technology, the task of science is the activity from acquiring new knowledge about nature, society and thinking to its practical application, what technology is.

Key words: science, information, knowledge, innovation.

In today's conditions, the wide implementation of the most advanced information and communication technologies is gaining priority. According to the program adopted in this area, our president Sh. Mirziyoyev said, "We need to further develop telecommunication technologies, communication systems and infrastructures, form information system complexes and the information base of the Electronic Government".

Science is a set of objective knowledge about the world. The task of science includes activities from creating new knowledge about nature, society and thinking to their implementation.

By the middle of the 20th century, the role of science in social life increased to an unprecedented level. Revolutions occurred in the field of science and technology, which was called the scientific and technical revolution.

The scientific and technical revolution of the late 40s of the 20th century, as a result of the direct transformation of science into production forces, led to great changes in the quality of technology and production in science itself.

Since the Middle Ages, universities have played an important role in the development of science in Europe. Religious and secular knowledge was taught in the madrasahs that arose in Central Asia. If we look at the scientific and technical development during the next quarter of a century, we will see that during this period, many specific sciences such as physics, mathematics, chemistry and biology, as well as laws and theories with completely new qualities and principles were created.

Today's rising science and technology has allowed us to understand the laws of society and the essence of natural phenomena, the development of the environment that surrounds it. Thanks to technology, a person actively cooperates with the environment, his living conditions are improved.

Technology is a set of processes and methods of mastering raw materials aimed at obtaining a product that meets the given parameters. This word entered science in 1872. The word technology embodies the sum of knowledge about the

methods and means of implementing the planned process, as well as the quality changes that occur in the object. Increasing the position of the national science and innovation system in socio-economic development, developing innovative activities in the regions. in order to increase the intellectual and technological potential of the regions, to form a modern infrastructure for the development of scientific and innovative activities, and to commercialize the results of scientific and scientific and technical activities in the Action Strategy for 2017-2021. a presidential decree on establishing a science financing and support fund by annexing the youth support fund was established.

All these are the opportunities given to us youth by the head of the country. We, the youth, must use the opportunities given to us correctly and effectively, raise the flag of our country to the sky through our knowledge. After all, they are trusting us, and we must justify this trust, because it is the duty of each of us to contribute to the development of our country by creating modern science and technology.

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